

Lesson evaluation questionnaire

		Expected answer	Link to the process evaluation objective
1. SCHOOL GENERAL INFORMATION			
1.1	District	Burera Kicukiro Muhanga Musanze Ngororero Nyagatare Ruhango Rusizi Rwamagana	
1.2	School code	School name	
1.3	Lesson	Test session Lesson 1: Health actions Lesson 2: Health claims Lesson 3: Unreliable claims Lesson 4: Reliable claims Lesson 5: Using what we learned (1) Lesson 6: Randomly created groups Lesson 7: Large-enough groups Lesson 8: Personal choices Lesson 9: Community choices Lesson 10: Using what we learned (2)	
2. Lesson preparation			
2.1	How long did it take you to prepare the lesson (minutes)	Number	Objective 1 & 3
2.2	How would you rate the level of preparedness	Very unprepared, Unprepared, Prepar	Objective 1 & 3
2.3	What made the preparation easy or difficult for you	text	Objective 1 & 3
3. Lesson Delivery			
3.1	Planned date of lesson delivery	Date	Objective 1
3.2	Actual date of lesson delivery	Date	Objective 1
3.3	Was there a change to the planned date of delivery	yes/no	Objective 1
3.4	If yes explain what happened	text	Objective 1
3.5	Mode of delivery	blackboard/projector	Objective 1
3.6	Was there a change to the mode of delivery	yes/no	Objective 1 & 3
3.7	If yes explain what happened	text	Objective 1 & 3
3.8	Number of students attended the lesson	number	Objective 1
3.9	Time used in lesson delivery (minutes)	number	Objective 1 & 3
3.10	Overall, how easy or difficult was it to teach the lesson	Very difficult, difficult, easy, Very easy	Objective 3
3.11	What made this lesson easy or difficult to teach	text	Objective 3
4. Overall objective of the lesson			
4.1	How would you rate the extent to which lesson objectives were	Too little achieved, Unachieved, Achie	Objective 3
4.2	Why do you think the lesson objectives were/were not achieved	text	Objective 3